

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR PREPARING PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS FOR INTERNATIONAL PIRLS ASSESSMENT

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Abstract. *This article talks about the methodological foundations of preparing primary school students to control the international assessment program PIRLS by developing their logical, analytical, critical, creative and independent thinking skills.*

Keywords: *Literary education, literary analysis and interpretation, didactic rule, deduction, induction, critical, creative, independent thinking, creative abilities.*

It is supported that in connection with the widespread introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies into the education system in the modern conditions of globalization, the implementation of students' creative abilities through the formation of logical, analytical, critical, creative, independent thinking skills is an important aspect of personality-oriented development. Education is of great importance in raising the younger generation to a level that meets the requirements of the world standard. In particular, the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study, dedicated to monitoring reading literacy in elementary grades, bears great responsibility for teaching reading in meeting the PIRLS requirements.

Moreover, the PIRLS program, organized by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA), aims to determine the level of primary school students' proficiency in reading in countries with a developed education system and to highlight notable aspects of the system of countries participating in the study, aimed at teaching.

Although there is a significant difference in the age of students in the countries participating in the monitoring of the quality of reading and comprehension of text in primary schools according to the world standard (in England, New Zealand, Finland children start from the age of five, in many countries they study from the age of six or seven), the demand is the same for everyone [2; 8].

The main goal of monitoring the quality of education according to the requirements of PIRLS or FIMSS, that is, the quality and trends of reading literacy, is to periodically study and control the results obtained at different times on different samples using different educational tools. It is to compare and draw appropriate conclusions. If we approach from this point of view, then in the education system of Uzbekistan, the issue of achieving reading literacy is relevant, that is, ensuring the speech competence of students, such as listening comprehension, reading comprehension, speaking and writing.

The fourth year of primary education is an important stage in the development of children. During this period, students must learn to study at a level that should ensure their successful acquisition of knowledge and skills at the next stage of education [].

Students who complete the fourth grade of primary school in 2021 will be assessed based on the PIRLS program in two different types of learning: during learning and extracurricular activities. In this:

-defining the level of learning in order to acquire the experience of learning in the literary education system;

-it is designed to determine the level of learning associated with the acquisition of information given in the educational process and its practical use.

According to the conceptual rules of the study, students' ability to read fiction and popular science texts is assessed according to the following 4 criteria:

- identifying the information given in the text; (using the analysis of scientific and popular texts as an example)

- drawing conclusions (literary analysis);

- interpreting and summarizing data (literary analysis);

- analyzing the content of the text, linguistic features and structure (literary analysis).

It is supported that analysis of popular science and fiction works helps students understand the content of the work, feel the events in the work with all their souls, perceive the work as an art of words, be able to evaluate the actions of the characters, be able to draw independent conclusions from them and, faced with such events, prepare to edit. In this regard, in primary education it is necessary to approach the analysis of popular science and fiction works from a scientific point of view. For this purpose, for students of the faculty of primary education of higher education, in addition to the subject "Native Language and Children's Literature", it is necessary to organize courses of theoretical and methodological training in literary analysis of popular science and fiction works. Children's Literature and it would be appropriate to include the topic of literary analysis in it. The subject "Methodology of Teaching Native Language in Primary Schools" methodically prepares students - future primary school teachers, so this issue cannot be attributed to this subject.

Additionally, preparing 4th-grade students for reading literacy for the international PIRLS control based on the textbook "Book for reading" and to help primary school teachers, Bakieva H. "Literary analysis in reading lessons in the 4th grade" A teaching aid called "Formation of skills" was created. This manual takes into account the pedagogical experience associated with this problem and its solution. In addition, methodological manuals for teaching students reading literacy, i.e. analysis of popular science and fiction works, were recommended. They cannot be called sufficient [4; 56].

The international PIRLS requirements depend, first of all, on the literary and artistic, social, spiritual, educational level of the text recommended for reading and analysis. Textbooks should include works that encourage students to independent and creative thinking. The reader needs to feel that a good work creates various experiences in the reader (sadness, anxiety), encourages him to think, allows him to choose his own position. The tasks given on the text of the work should ensure the reading literacy of students. In this regard, our textbooks have shortcomings.

Also, it can be seen that raising the reading literacy of students to a high level largely depends on the teacher's knowledge of text analysis and pedagogical skills.

If the textbook texts are checked for their interestingness, vitality, artistic perfection and the content of the questions posed at the end of the text, then you can see texts that cannot stimulate students' emotions, cannot enrich their imagination and, on the contrary, extinguish their interests. For example, in the 3rd grade "Books for reading" based on the story of Khamidulla Murodov "New House", 3rd graders are asked to carry sand, bricks, soil with them to the construction site

and they go to work on the construction site. After reading this story, does the work meet the requirements of the international standard? the question arises.

Definitely, the tale of Gozal Begim "Sister of the River" in the 3rd paragraph, what does the proverb used in the tale mean, "Why did the sisters Syr Darya and Zarafshon have golden ears?", "Animals and plants go to school" (?) What is the "power of language" in the text "The Power of Language" (narrative)? Polat Momin's poem "Independence from Harmony" is made up of dry advice, it is impossible to find a basis that will convince and surprise the reader. In Mukhabbat Khamidova's story "Knowledge of the Homeland" we see a very interesting life story of the author, but we do not see logic in the system of events, the plot is artificial. Also in the work "Homeland" things are listed that are seen through the eyes of a child. Events do not encourage the student to think and think, do not develop artistic and aesthetic taste, do not develop the personality of the student. Kavsar Turdiyeva poetically expresses what the reader sees in the poem "Around the Prosperous Neighborhood":

- Our District
- In every apartment and house.
- Full of love
- It gets better [5;84]

The following paragraphs are no exception. The ambiguity of content and logic has also affected its language.

In relation to the text of the work included in the textbook, questions should be asked aimed at a deep understanding of its content, independent research and creative thinking, connection with life, summing up, and speech development.

It is known that textbooks pay little attention to information related to the artistry of the work, the features of the language, the connection of plot events, characterization of characters, and general conclusions. It is necessary to take into account that preparing students for the international PIRLS reading literacy tests is not just a one-time formal event, but an important place in the future plan of primary education.

It is known that in connection with reading works of art, the formation of artistic and aesthetic thinking of students in a personality-oriented education system aimed at self-awareness, the development of a sense of love for the Motherland, reading education, a special place is occupied by the study of samples of children's literature as works of art.

Nowadays, primary school teachers need clearly substantiated, scientifically based instructions on reading methods. The methodology gives the future primary school teacher the opportunity to independently, consciously approach the content of literary education and its teaching, not only to study the experience of others, but also consciously analyze the results of their activities and correctly focus on ensuring their ability to draw conclusions [1; 48].

The following didactic principles can be attributed to the basis of teaching methods in elementary grades:

1. Education should have a comprehensive impact on the understanding of students.
2. Students clearly understand the problem.
3. The teacher must be able to demonstrate new complex educational problems in the context of familiar events. Adabiy ta'lim jarayonida deduksiyani induksiya bilan bog'lay bilishi [3;177].

Modern literary education is aimed at mastering those cultural resources that have been created and enriched throughout the history of mankind for centuries, preparing them for real life, making an informed choice of profession, and teaching civilized behavior with the people around them. To do this, it is necessary to clearly define teaching methods, goals, and objectives at each stage of literary education, taking into account the educational capabilities of students.

A deep understanding of the features of a work of art as an artistic phenomenon, the application of existing literary knowledge and concepts to the analysis of planned works ensures the quality and effectiveness of reading classes.

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